

Scale-Aware Adaptive Feature Quantization for Robust Medical Image Representation Learning (Supplementary)

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Table 1. Class-wise performance analysis of our proposed approach using DenseNet121 as the backbone encoder on the NIH Chest X-ray dataset. The table presents Accuracy (ACC), Precision, Recall, and F1 scores for each medical condition. The last row shows the mean performance across all conditions, highlighting the overall effectiveness of the model.

Condition	ACC	Precision	Recall	F1
Atelectasis	87.18	50.00	13.26	20.90
Cardiomegaly	95.95	54.73	17.30	26.32
Consolidation	92.91	35.00	0.39	0.76
Infiltration	75.41	46.55	19.94	27.86
Pneumothorax	89.87	54.97	15.35	24.11
Edema	96.35	38.46	2.16	4.09
Emphysema	97.09	55.73	25.80	35.29
Fibrosis	98.28	25.00	0.92	1.77
Effusion	83.91	59.46	36.45	45.19
Pneumonia	97.84	50.00	9.01	15.27
Pleural_Thick.	95.39	27.78	2.19	4.07
Nodule	93.63	49.19	7.52	13.05
Mass	92.99	47.20	23.17	31.07
Hernia	99.73	72.97	31.40	43.90
Normal	71.81	67.30	52.10	58.71
Mean	91.22	49.80	16.83	23.01

1 Class-wise analysis on NIH Dataset:

Table 1 provides the class-wise performance analysis of our proposed approach using DenseNet121 as the backbone encoder for various medical conditions in chest X-rays. With a mean accuracy of 91.22% across all conditions, the model demonstrates strong overall performance. However, the disparity between mean precision (49.80%) and mean recall (16.83%) suggests a conservative prediction strategy that favors precision over recall. However, the performance varies significantly across different conditions, with Normal cases showing the most balanced performance (F1 score of 58.71%, precision 67.30%, recall 52.10%). Rare conditions such as Fibrosis, Consolidation, and Pleural Thickening exhibit relatively very high precision but extremely low recall, pointing to potential underdiagnosis. Notably, Hernia detection also shows high precision (72.97%) but lower recall (31.40%), suggesting high confidence in positive predictions but possible missed cases. Further, compared to the standard CNN model

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and the best baseline method VQSA, our method performs comparatively better with considerable performance gains. Our mean precision (49.80%), recall (16.83%), and F1 score (23.01%) show significant improvements over these baseline models, indicating the effectiveness of our proposed approach. However, despite these improvements and the high overall performance metrics, a deeper analysis reveals potential issues that could impact the model’s effectiveness. The varied performance across conditions underscores the complexity of multi-label chest X-ray classification, which requires tailored approaches to enhance the overall diagnostic capabilities and their practical utility in clinical environments.

2 Performance Comparison with Standard CNN Models:

Table 2 presents additional evaluation metrics (precision and recall) beyond those reported in the main paper (Table 1) for NIH-Chest-Xray-14 and the ISIC-2018 dataset. These results provide a more comprehensive performance analysis of the proposed multi-scale dynamic vector quantization method compared to standard CNN models. In the NIH dataset, specifically on precision, we observe consistent enhancements, with performance gain ranging from 9.1 to 17.3 percentage points. Recall values also consistently improved, with gains ranging from 2.9 to 7.9 percentage points. In precision on the skin session dataset also, we observe consistent improvements with gains ranging from 1.0 to 3.8 percentage points. Recall values, which in this case are identical to the accuracy improvements, also show consistent enhancements across all models. These additional metrics further reinforce the effectiveness of the proposed method, demonstrating that it not only improves overall performance (as shown by AUC, Accuracy, and F1 scores in the main paper) but also enhances the models’ ability to correctly identify positive cases (improved recall) while reducing false positives (improved precision).

3 Comparison with SOTA Baseline Methods:

Table 3 presents the comparison of our proposed method with SOTA approaches for the NIH Chest-Xray-14 and skin lesion classification task. While the main paper reported AUC and F1 scores for the NIH and Accuracy and F1 scores for the ISIC data (Table 2), this table provides additional metrics, specifically Precision and Recall, offering a more precise view of the models’ performance. Specifically, our

Table 2. Comparative performance analysis of our method vs. standard CNN Models on the clean test set samples of NIH Chest-Xray-14 and ISIC-2018 datasets. The table presents mean Precision and Recall metrics for various CNN architectures. "Standard" refers to the standard CNN implementation, while "Ours" represents the proposed method. Green arrows (\uparrow) indicate performance improvements compared to the respective standard CNN model in percentage points.

Methods	NIH Chest-Xray-14				ISIC-2018			
	Precision		Recall		Precision		Recall	
	Standard	Ours	Standard	Ours	Standard	Ours	Standard	Ours
Resnet18	24.8	41.7 (\uparrow 16.9)	08.4	15.9 (\uparrow 7.5)	80.9	82.2 (\uparrow 1.3)	81.2	82.4 (\uparrow 1.2)
Densenet121	33.3	49.8 (\uparrow 16.5)	09.9	16.8 (\uparrow 6.9)	80.0	83.8 (\uparrow 3.8)	80.3	84.0 (\uparrow 3.7)
Densenet161	32.6	45.8 (\uparrow 13.2)	08.9	16.8 (\uparrow 7.9)	78.9	82.4 (\uparrow 3.5)	79.2	82.8 (\uparrow 3.6)
Densenet201	33.9	43.0 (\uparrow 09.1)	11.0	16.2 (\uparrow 5.2)	82.4	83.4 (\uparrow 1.0)	82.8	83.8 (\uparrow 1.0)
Efficientnet_b0	32.0	49.3 (\uparrow 17.3)	10.8	17.7 (\uparrow 5.9)	80.5	83.7 (\uparrow 3.2)	81.0	83.2 (\uparrow 2.2)
Efficientnet_b2	33.9	44.9 (\uparrow 11.0)	11.4	16.3 (\uparrow 4.9)	81.4	83.1 (\uparrow 1.7)	81.4	83.5 (\uparrow 2.1)
Efficientnet_b4	33.4	47.6 (\uparrow 14.2)	11.5	14.4 (\uparrow 2.9)	82.0	83.1 (\uparrow 1.1)	82.1	83.2 (\uparrow 1.1)
Mobilenet_v2	31.4	42.9 (\uparrow 11.5)	12.1	16.0 (\uparrow 3.9)	80.9	82.5 (\uparrow 1.6)	80.2	81.9 (\uparrow 1.7)

Table 3. Comparison of our proposed method with SOTA approaches. The table presents test set results for clean NIH Chest-Xray-14 and ISIC-2018 Classifications. Green arrows (\uparrow) indicate performance improvements compared to the best baseline method (VQSA). Bold numbers represent the best performance, while underlined numbers indicate the second-best results.

Methods	NIH Chest-Xray-14		ISIC-2018	
	Precision	Recall	Precision	Recall
MedViT	17.6	05.5	66.6	70.3
SEViT	16.4	05.1	67.4	71.0
QualNet	35.8	12.8	78.2	78.4
VQSA	37.3	13.2	80.5	80.6
Ours	49.8 (\uparrow 12.5) 16.8 (\uparrow 03.6)	83.8 (\uparrow 03.3) 84.0 (\uparrow 03.4)		

Table 4. Performance comparison on perturbed NIH Chest X-ray test data. Models trained with varying ratios of clean/perturbed samples. Results show Precision and Recall for standard CNN, VQSA, and our method using the Densenet121 backbone.

Clean(%)	Precision			Recall		
	Standard	VQSA	Ours	Standard	VQSA	Ours
50	31.5	30.9	40.4	08.2	10.0	12.5
60	32.1	34.9	40.0	08.1	09.7	11.1
70	33.1	32.1	39.9	08.0	09.1	11.5
80	31.4	32.2	40.0	08.9	08.6	13.5
90	30.0	31.8	44.5	08.1	09.0	14.1
100	26.5	29.2	32.6	06.6	07.7	11.3

method demonstrates a substantial improvement in precision compared to the best baseline methods. In NIH, it achieves a precision of 49.8%, which is a significant increase of 12.5 percentage points over VQSA’s 37.3%. The proposed method also shows a notable improvement in recall. It achieves a recall of 16.8%, which is an increase of 3.6 percentage points over VQSA’s 13.2%. On ISIC-2018, our proposed method also demonstrated better precision compared to baseline methods by showing an increase of 3.3 percentage points compared to VQSA. In the case of recall also, it achieves a recall of 84.0%, which is an increase of 3.4 percentage points over VQSA’s 80.6%. These additional metrics provide valuable insights beyond the AUC, Accuracy, and F1 scores reported in the main paper. The improvements in both precision and recall indicate that our method excels in reducing false positives (high precision) while still capturing a good proportion of true positives (improved recall).

Table 5. Performance comparison of models with and without Dynamic Quantization (DQ) on NIH Chest-Xray-14 test set. Results show Precision and Recall across various CNN architectures.

Methods	Precision		Recall	
	w/o DQ	w/ DQ	w/o DQ	w/ DQ
Resnet18	40.1	41.7 (\uparrow 1.6)	10.7	15.9 (\uparrow 5.2)
Densenet121	43.7	49.8 (\uparrow 6.1)	15.8	16.8 (\uparrow 1.0)
Densenet161	44.1	45.8 (\uparrow 1.7)	16.4	16.8 (\uparrow 0.8)
Densenet201	39.6	43.0 (\uparrow 3.4)	14.8	16.2 (\uparrow 1.4)
Efficientnet_b0	36.8	49.3 (\uparrow 12.3)	11.3	17.7 (\uparrow 6.4)
Efficientnet_b2	35.4	44.9 (\uparrow 9.5)	14.3	16.3 (\uparrow 3.0)
Efficientnet_b4	39.4	47.6 (\uparrow 8.2)	12.3	14.4 (\uparrow 2.1)
Mobilenet_v2	35.4	42.9 (\uparrow 7.5)	13.4	16.0 (\uparrow 2.6)

4 Robustness on NIH:

Table 4 reported the additional precision and recall evaluation metrics in addition to AUC and F1 (reported in the main paper, Table 3). These results provide a more comprehensive view of our model’s performance and robustness when dealing with perturbed NIH Chest X-ray test data. Analyzing the precision metrics, we observe that our proposed method consistently outperforms both the standard CNN and VQSA across all clean data ratios. Notably, when trained on entirely clean data (100% clean) and tested on perturbed data, our method achieves a precision of 32.6%, compared to 26.5% and 29.2% for the standard CNN and VQSA, respectively. As we introduce perturbed samples into the training data, we see a general trend of improving precision across all methods. Our method maintains its lead, reaching a peak precision of 44.5% when trained on 90% clean and 10% perturbed data. This suggests that exposure to a small amount of perturbed data during training significantly enhances the model’s ability to handle perturbations during testing. The recall metrics show a similar pattern. Our method consistently outperforms the other approaches, with the gap widening as more perturbed data is introduced in training. At 90% clean / 10% perturbed training data, our method achieves a recall of 14.1%, compared to 8.1% and 9.0% for the standard CNN and VQSA. This indicates that our approach is better at identifying true positive cases in perturbed data.

5 Ablation Study

5.1 Impact of Dynamic Quantization (DQ) as part of the Ablation study:

Table 5 presents additional metrics (precision and recall) to complement the AUC and F1 scores reported in Table 5 of the main paper. This provides a more comprehensive view of the impact of Dynamic Quantization (DQ) on weighing the different scales' quantized features across various CNN architectures on the NIH Chest-Xray-14 test set. Note that precision shows consistent improvements with the application of DQ across all architectures. The most notable enhancement is observed in EfficientNet_b0, with a substantial increase of 12.3 percentage points (from 36.8% to 49.3%). Other architectures also demonstrate significant gains, with improvements ranging from 1.6 to 9.5 percentage points. Recall metrics similarly benefit from DQ, with all architectures showing enhancements. These results indicate that dynamic quantization not only improves the overall performance (as evidenced by AUC and F1 scores reported earlier) but also enhances the model's ability to correctly identify positive cases (improved precision) while maintaining or improving its capability to capture true positives (improved recall). This consistent improvement across different architectures and metrics underscores the effectiveness of DQ in enhancing model performance for medical image classification tasks by adaptively selecting the most informative feature across different scales (fine-medium- and coarse-grained).

6 Visualizing Model Performance on NIH:

Fig. 1 presents a comparison of GradCAM visualizations and confidence scores for our proposed method against the standard CNN model and VQSA, using DenseNet121 as the backbone. The figure showcases eight different cases, each representing various medical conditions commonly found in chest X-rays. Our proposed method demonstrates notable improvements in both feature localization and confidence scoring across these diverse cases. The GradCAM heatmaps generated by our model consistently show more precise and focused activation in the pathological regions of interest. This improved localization is particularly evident in complex cases, such as the case of Effusion and Atelectasis, where our model more accurately highlights the affected areas. In terms of confidence scoring, our method exhibits higher sigmoid scores for the correct classes, indicating increased certainty in its predictions. Similarly, for the Pneumothorax case, our method shows a more focused activation on the relevant region of the lung, accompanied by a higher confidence score. This shows that our proposed method not only improves the accuracy of predictions but also enhances the model's ability to localize pathological regions with high confidence.

7 Analysis of ISIC-2018 Classification Results:

To interpret the decision-making process of our models, we employ GradCAM visualizations (Fig 2) for representative samples from each skin lesion class, comparing the results across three methods (Standard CNN model, VQSA, and Ours). The GradCAM visualizations from our proposed approach show more focused and precise activation in clinically relevant areas of the lesions with relatively higher confidence compared to the other two methods. These GradCAM results provide evidence that our proposed approach is not only more accurate but also more interpretable, focusing on medically relevant features for its classifications.

Standard	VQSA	Ours	Standard	VQSA	Ours
Actual class: Infiltration			Actual class: Effusion		
0.62121 Atelectasis 0.33384 Infiltration 0.23050 No Finding 0.22014 Effusion 0.11071 Consolidation	0.30273 No Finding 0.24249 Infiltration 0.08898 Effusion 0.08293 Emphysema 0.08272 Atelectasis	0.49430 Infiltration 0.41386 Atelectasis 0.21132 Effusion 0.19458 No Finding 0.12308 Consolidation	0.39779 Effusion 0.35118 Infiltration 0.26162 No Finding 0.26025 Atelectasis 0.15498 Consolidation	0.27281 Infiltration 0.17610 No Finding 0.11021 Emphysema 0.10005 Atelectasis 0.09436 Effusion	0.58851 Effusion 0.29203 Atelectasis 0.26846 Infiltration 0.21789 No Finding 0.13295 Consolidation
Actual class: Pneumothorax			Actual class: Mass		
0.52030 Pneumothorax 0.36844 Emphysema 0.23627 No Finding 0.17507 Atelectasis 0.11495 Pleural_Thickening	0.20779 Infiltration 0.16375 Effusion 0.15069 No Finding 0.12546 Cardiomegaly 0.12008 Emphysema	0.87632 Pneumothorax 0.61218 Emphysema 0.09311 Mass 0.07449 Effusion 0.06437 No Finding	0.37452 No Finding 0.20324 Infiltration 0.15026 Mass 0.13922 Nodule 0.07218 Effusion	0.27475 No Finding 0.23501 Infiltration 0.14012 Atelectasis 0.13400 Effusion 0.10994 Nodule	0.49060 Nodule 0.30479 Mass 0.20595 No Finding 0.11431 Infiltration 0.09373 Effusion
Actual class: No Finding			Actual class: Cardiomegaly		
0.69303 No Finding 0.12914 Infiltration 0.04963 Atelectasis 0.04872 Nodule 0.02600 Mass	0.27492 No Finding 0.26236 Effusion 0.12726 Infiltration 0.11834 Atelectasis 0.10080 Pleural_Thickening	0.87240 No Finding 0.04154 Infiltration 0.03696 Atelectasis 0.01125 Nodule 0.01036 Effusion	0.55340 No Finding 0.29530 Cardiomegaly 0.12880 Infiltration 0.07325 Atelectasis 0.05379 Effusion	0.29022 No Finding 0.18581 Effusion 0.13458 Infiltration 0.11479 Pleural_Thickening 0.11308 Nodule	0.61783 Cardiomegaly 0.33195 No Finding 0.20065 Infiltration 0.11112 Atelectasis 0.11076 Effusion
Actual class: Effusion, Atelectasis			Actual class: Atelectasis		
0.60444 Atelectasis 0.33916 Effusion 0.21361 Infiltration 0.20852 No Finding 0.09766 Consolidation	0.27277 Infiltration 0.22300 No Finding 0.09272 Effusion 0.07985 Atelectasis 0.06714 Nodule	0.64471 Effusion 0.63535 Atelectasis 0.19326 Infiltration 0.14310 No Finding 0.12304 Consolidation	0.71049 No Finding 0.17050 Atelectasis 0.10298 Infiltration 0.02126 Effusion 0.01687 Consolidation	0.30505 No Finding 0.20564 Infiltration 0.09807 Effusion 0.09062 Nodule 0.06937 Atelectasis	0.59894 Atelectasis 0.42741 No Finding 0.13997 Infiltration 0.03880 Effusion 0.00743 Consolidation

Figure 1. GradCAM visualizations and confidence scores comparison using DenseNet121 backbone. Each row shows GradCAM heatmaps (top) and top 5 predictions with sigmoid scores (bottom) for different cases. Our method demonstrates improved feature localization and confidence scoring, especially for the challenging Hernia case.

Figure 2. GradCAM visualizations for representative skin lesion samples from the ISIC-2018 dataset corresponding to the standard CNN, VQSA, and our proposed method using Densenet121 architecture.